

BIOCHEMICAL CHANGES IN BACTERIA IRRADIATED WITH ULTRAVIOLET LIGHT

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Ultraviolet irradiation in sublethal dose of certain gram-negative micro-organisms has been found to cause considerable alteration of their biochemical characters. Methyl red reaction and indole formation increase generally; irradiated *Shigella sonnei* and *Pseudomonas pyocyaneus* form indole; citrate utilisation, Voges-Proskauer reaction and nitrate reduction decrease. In most of the organisms fermentation characters regarding sugars and alcohols are altered.

Works on the effects of irradiation on micro-organisms were in the past largely directed to the study of lethal effect. More recently (Lewis, *J. Bact.*, 1934, 28, 616; Stewart, *J. Hyg.*, 1942, 41, 497) ultraviolet and other irradiations have been used for bacterial mutations. Mukherji (*Ind. J. Med. Res.*, 1952, 40, 167) has shown that smears of gram-negative bacteria on irradiation for two hours change to gram-positive. The present work deals with biochemical changes in bacteria effected by irradiation with UV light.

EXPERIMENTAL

Light as emitted from a portable Hanovia UV lamp with a deep violet filter was used in this work. The wave-lengths of the light emitted lie between 2000 and 3000Å. The light caused erythema of the skin with a subject of light wheat colour, when exposed for a minimum of nine minutes at a distance of one metre.

The various bacteria used in this work were grown in ordinary nutrient broth of pH 7.2 for 18 hours at 37° and a few drops from these cultures were introduced in quartz tubes containing the same quality of nutrient broth so as to contain about 250 million organisms per cm³. The quartz tubes were obtained from Heraus Quarzglaswerke, Hanau, Germany. The external diameter is approximately 8.5 mm and the internal diameter, 7 mm. After inoculation the quartz tubes were kept at a mean temperature of 35° and exposed to the UV light from the Hanovia lamp at a distance of one metre from the bulb for a period of 3 hours with occasional shaking. The shaking was done with a view to effecting as uniform an exposure of the culture mass as possible to the radiation of the UV light. A set of ten sugar tubes containing 1% each of different sugars in ordinary nutrient broth with Andrade's indicator and media for the testing of methyl red, the Voges-Proskauer's reaction, indole formation, citrate utilisation and nitrate reduction were inoculated with one drop each of the irradiated cultures. Control tests with each of the cultures, which were grown in nutrient broth for 3 hours at 35° (but not irradiated), were also put up simultaneously. The inoculated tubes for the Voges-Proskauer test were incubated at 30° and others at 37°

for 5 days. This was found necessary since the *Aerobacter aerogenes* used in this work is V.P. positive only, when incubated at this temperature. In the case of the Voges-Proskauer, methyl red and ether tests, 3 drops of culture were inoculated in 3 c.c. of the medium. Opacity of the various culture tubes including sugars was found to be almost the same in 24 hours in irradiated and control cultures.

TABLE I

Biochemical reactions.

Bacteria.	Methyl red.		Citrate utilisation.		Indole formation.		Nitrate reduction.	
	Irrad.	Contr.	Irrad.	Contr.	Irrad.	Contr.	Irrad.	Contr.
<i>S. paratyphi</i>	+++	++	+	++	-	-	Trace	+
<i>S. schottmuleri</i>	+++	++	+	++	-	-	Trace	+
<i>S. typhi</i>	+++	++	+	++	-	-	Trace	+
<i>E. coli</i>	++++	++	+++	+++	+++	++	+	++
<i>A. aerogenes</i>	-	-	++	+++	+++	+	Trace	++
<i>P. pyocyaneus</i>	-	Trace	++	+++	+++	+, -	Trace	+
<i>Sh. dysenteriae</i>	++	+	-	-	-	-	Trace	+
<i>Sh. paradysenteriae</i>	++	+	-	-	++	-	-	-
<i>Sh. sonnei</i>	++	+	-	Trace	++	-	-	-
<i>B. subtilis</i>	++	+	+++	++++	-	-	Trace	+

N.B. +, ++, +++, +++++ indicate the reaction to be just positive, moderately positive, strongly positive and very strongly positive, respectively; - denotes negative.

TABLE II

Fermentation of sugars and alcohols.

Bacteria.	Glucose.		Lactose.		Mannite.		Mannose.		Maltose.	
	Irr.	Contr.								
<i>S. paratyphi</i>	+	+	⊥	±	⊥	+	⊥	+	⊥	+
<i>S. schottmuleri</i>	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	+
<i>S. typhi</i>	⊥	⊥	⊥	⊥	⊥	⊥	⊥	⊥	⊥	⊥
<i>E. coli</i>	+	+	±	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>A. aerogenes</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	⊥	+
<i>P. pyocyaneus</i>	⊥	⊥	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Sh. dysenteriae</i>	⊥	⊥	⊥	-	-	-	⊥	-	⊥	-
<i>Sh. paradysenteriae</i>	⊥	⊥	⊥	-	⊥	⊥	⊥	-	⊥	⊥
<i>Sh. sonnei</i>	⊥	⊥	⊥	⊥	⊥	⊥	⊥	⊥	⊥	⊥
<i>B. subtilis</i>	⊥	⊥	⊥	-	-	⊥	⊥	⊥	⊥	⊥

N.B. + denotes acid and gas; ⊥ denotes gas and - denotes no reaction

TABLE III

Fermentation of sugars and alcohols.

Bacteria.	Arbinose.		Dulcitol.		Sorbitol.		Sucrose.		Xylose.	
	Irr.	Contr.	Irr.	Contr.	Irr.	Contr.	Irr.	Contr.	Irr.	Co.,tr.
<i>S. paratyphi</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	-
<i>S. schottmulleri</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+
<i>S. typhi</i>	+	-	+	-	+	+	±	-	+	+
<i>E. coli</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+
<i>A. aerogenes</i>	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>P. pyocyaneus</i>	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	+
<i>Sh. dysenteriae</i>	+	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	-
<i>Sh. paradysenteriae</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	-
<i>Sh. sonnei</i>	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	+
<i>B. subtilis</i>	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+

N.B. Symbols have the same significance as in Table II.

DISCUSSION

It will be observed that irradiation with ultraviolet light brings about certain changes in the living bacteria. That the bacteria remain alive after three hours' irradiation has been very carefully tested. Besides the fact that the bacteria are capable of fermenting sugars and alcohols and bring about other biochemical changes, growth is also evident from the opacity of the media inoculated. The irradiated bacteria were subcultured in sugar media for two more generations in the case of *P. pyocyaneus* and *Sh. sonnei*. Fermentation of sugars did take place as with the first generation of the irradiated culture. These irradiated *E. coli* and *S. typhi*, when grown with phage isolated from local patients, supported the growth of the phage. Therefore the unavoidable conclusion is that the bacteria after irradiation remain viable.

Methyl red reaction is substantially increased with all the irradiated bacteria, excepting in the cases of *A. aerogenes* and *P. pyocyaneus*, which are normally negative. Further, indole formation is not only increased with irradiated *E. coli*, *A. aerogenes*, *Shigella paradysenteriae* Flexner, but *Sh. sonnei* and *P. pyocyaneus*, which do not normally form indole, begin to produce this substance after irradiation with ultraviolet light. On the other hand, ultraviolet irradiation considerably decreases the Voges-Proskauer reaction with *A. aerogenes*, and citrate utilisation and nitrate reduction with *S. paratyphi*, *S. schottmuelleri*, *S. typhi*, *E. coli* (this particular strain utilised citrate for its growth), *A. aerogenes*, *P. pyocyaneus* and *B. subtilis*. Nitrate reduction with irradiated *Sh. dysenteriae*, Shiga was also inhibited.

Fermentations of various sugars and alcohols have been found to be constant with irradiated *Sh. sonnei* and *P. pyocyaneus*. With other irradiated bacteria, while certain types of fermentations were nearly constant, occasionally there were partial or complete inhibition of a particular fermentation or even a change from only acid production to one of acid and gas.

Irradiated *P. pyocyaneus* and *Sh. sonnei* produced more or less the same type of sugar fermentations in all the three generations. The detailed genetic study is being undertaken for a subsequent communication. No special explanation for the changed biochemical properties are being attempted in this paper beyond stating the relevant work of Spiegel-Adolf (*Med. Rec.*, 1939, 155, 430) that ultraviolet light brings about an alteration in the proteins and therefore also of the enzymes.

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